

EFFECT OF MICROWAVES AGAINST WAREHOUSE PESTS

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Abstract. *The article describes the results of using microwaves in protecting leguminous products from pests.*

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As is known, during the period of storage of grain legume products (mung beans, peas, etc.), dried fruits (apricots, sour figs, dried raisins), stored in warehouses and apartments, the grains become completely unsuitable not only for consumption, but also for consumption for food. also for plantings resulting from bruxus lesions.

According to Academician N.D. Zakharov, research conducted in recent years on in-depth study of microwave technology in a new direction and its introduction into the agricultural complex is of great importance in the absorption of energy and the protection of various food products. , in increasing production and product quality. (1)

Italian scientist Niola Lmmacolata has obtained positive results in controlling insects that damage stored agricultural products by heating the food using microwaves. (2)

On the use of microwaves in food products, O. B. Babayants and others are conducting extensive scientific research in Ukraine. Taking this into account, the use of short-wave frequencies was chosen in order to search for simple, folk methods of combating pest larvae in grain in order to neutralize stored grain products.

In this case, 500 mung beans and mung beans were placed in bags and microwaved for 15 seconds, 30 seconds and 1 minute. After treatment, the mash and bean grains in bags were placed separately in jars and observed every 10-15 days, and the effectiveness was determined at 30 and 60 days. The results obtained showed that the effect of a short wave of 250 MHz on mushy grains in 1 minute (dispersal of mushy grains) averaged 1.3% per 500 mushy grains over 30 days, in the control - 30.2%, in the 60-day experiment - 1.3%. ...and in the control it was 64.4%.

The greatest positive effect was observed at 30 seconds and 1 minute on average in 0.4-0.8% of pests and in 75.4-81.0% of control insect larvae.

Taking this into account, processing with this method can only be carried out in the direction of nutrition.

REFERENCES

1. Zakharov N.D. - Microwave processing and cooking and culinary industry. Microwave technology and national economy, Vol. 2-3, Kyiv-Odessa, 2000. pp. 16-17.
2. Niola L. - Food product heated in a microwave oven. brush "Drying and fighting insects".
3. Babayants O.V. I am doctor. – The influence of MV-field on seed infection of winter wheat. Microwave technology and national economy, Vol. 2-3. Kyiv-Odessa 2000. P. 80-81.